

hydrolysis is in the following order : methyl acetate > ethyl acetate > methyl benzoate. The increase in the rate constant upto about 1.0 g (Fig. 4) may probably be due to the complete and uniform dispersion of the catalyst in the reaction vessel. Further additions beyond 1.0 g increase the bulk of the catalyst, but the ester molecules may not be able to reach the interior of the catalyst bulk and get adsorbed over the catalyst. Hence, the rates begin to fall.

The activation energy (E_a), frequency factor (PZ) and thermodynamic parameters ($\Delta G^\ddagger$, $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$) for the three systems were calculated using Arrhenius and Eyring's equation⁹ and the values are given in Table 2. The higher value of activation

TABLE 2—RATE CONSTANTS, FREQUENCY FACTOR AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR THE HYDROLYSIS OF METHYL ACETATE, ETHYL ACETATE AND METHYL BENZOATE OVER CATALYST A

Temp. K	$k \times 10^4$, sec ⁻¹	PZ $\times 10^{-3}$, sec ⁻¹	$\Delta H^\ddagger$, kJ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta G^\ddagger$, kJ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta S^\ddagger$, JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
Methyl Acetate $E_a = 44.18$ kJ mol ⁻¹					
302.0	5.746	2.514	41.672	98.540	-188.20
308.0	8.064	2.506	41.623	99.669	-188.50
314.0	11.171	2.494	41.579	100.800	-188.70
Ethyl Acetate $E_a = 52.42$ kJ mol ⁻¹					
309.5	8.090	82.45	49.901	100.60	-167.00
311.5	5.118	81.49	49.834	102.01	-167.50
319.5	8.251	80.63	49.567	103.48	-167.90
Methyl Benzoate $E_a = 67.01$ kJ mol ⁻¹					
309.5	1.083	8615	64.488	109.290	-127.84
313.5	2.506	8650	64.405	104.542	-128.02
328.0	7.942	8717	64.284	106.354	-128.26

energy for methyl benzoate may be due to the precipitation of benzoic acid over zinc oxide.

References

- G. W. DAVIES and C. G. THOMAS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 1609.
- R. VEDA, K. FUJIHARA and T. TERASHIMA, *J. Ferment. Tech. Jpn.*, 1956, 34, 183.
- S. A. BERNHARD and L. P. HAMMET, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 1798.
- S. P. WALVEKAR and A. B. HALGERI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 4, 246.
- A. E. BAILEY, "Industrial Oil and Fat Products", 1951, p. 805.
- C. H. MARSEL and D. ALLEN, *Chem. Engg.*, 1947, 54, 104.
- A. K. GOPALAN, N. DESIKACHAR and M. V. A. IYENGAR, *Chem. Age (India)*, 1959, 10, 577.
- A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", Longmans Green, London, 1948.
- S. GLASSTONE, K. J. LAIDLER and H. EYRING, "The Theory of Rate Processes", 1941, p. 197.

Conductometric Study of Interaction of Sodium *N*-Chlorobenzenesulphonamide with Silver(I), Mercury(II), Thorium(IV) and Zirconium(IV) Solutions**

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IN continuation of our work on organic haloamines¹⁻³, we report in this note the result of our studies on the reactions of chloramine-B with some metal ions.

Experimental

Silver nitrate, mercuric chloride, thorium chloride, thorium nitrate, zirconium oxychloride and zirconium nitrate were of AR grade and their solutions were prepared in triply distilled water. Aqueous solutions of chloramine-B¹ were standardized by the iodometric method. All other chemicals used were of reagent grade.

Conductance measurements were made at room temperature (27°) using a Phillips PR 9500 conductivity bridge with a dip type conductivity cell (cell constant : 0.66 cm⁻¹). Potentiometric titrations were carried out on an Elico model LI-120 digital pH meter.

Uv spectra were obtained on a Beckmann DB spectrophotometer and ir spectra (KBr) were obtained on a Carl-Zeiss UR-10 spectrophotometer.

The white precipitates obtained by the addition of chloramine-B (CAB) to silver nitrate and mercuric chloride solutions were filtered, washed repeatedly with water, dried and analysed. The compound of Ag^I analysed for C₆H₅SO₂NClAg (Found : Ag, 36.26 ; Cl, 11.73 ; S, 10.89 ; N, 4.65. Requires Ag, 36.18 ; Cl, 11.90 ; S, 10.72 ; N, 4.69%). The compound of Hg^{II} analysed for (C₆H₅SO₂NCl)₂Hg (Found : Hg, 34.82 ; Cl, 12.48 ; S, 11.1 ; N, 4.85. Requires Hg, 34.5 ; Cl, 12.20 ; S, 11.01 ; N, 4.82%). Silver compound decomposed at 155-160° and mercury compound at 140°. Aqueous solutions of both the compounds liberate iodine from acidified potassium iodide solution.

The compound obtained by the addition of a solution of Th^{IV} or Zr^{IV} to a solution of CAB was filtered, washed with water and was estimated iodometrically in glacial acetic acid medium. The unreacted CAB in the filtrate was also determined iodometrically. The amount of H⁺ reacted was calculated by titration against NaOH. It is found that CAB and H⁺ reacted approximately in 1 : 1 molar ratio and the amount of product formed is nearly half the amount of CAB reacted. The solid

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obtained in the reaction of $ZrOCl_2$ melted at 74° and analysed for dichloramine-B (DCB or $RNCl_2$) (Found : Cl, 30.9 ; S, 14.21 ; N, 6.3. Requires Cl, 31.4 ; S, 14.16 ; N, 6.19%).

Results and Discussion

Conductivity titration curves of $AgNO_3$ and $HgCl_2$ with CAB have shown breaks at 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratios, respectively, in accordance with the composition in solid state. The stoichiometric equations can be represented as in (1) and (2).

where R is $C_6H_5SO_3$. The uv and ir spectra of CAB, $RNClAg$ and $(RNCl)_2Hg$ are superimposable indicating that they are simple salts.

Similar conductivity titrations of thorium and zirconium solutions against CAB show breaks at 1 : 3 and 1 : 1 molar ratios, respectively. Carefully neutralised solutions of Th^{IV} and Zr^{IV} with NaOH were mixed with CAB, no precipitation was observed. These results indicate that H^+ produced, during the hydrolysis of these ions in aqueous solution is actually involved in the formation of DCB. The hydrolysis equilibria⁴ of Th^{IV} and Zr^{IV} in aqueous solution can be represented by equations (3) and (4).

The precipitate obtained could be dichloramine-B (DCB) which is only sparingly soluble in water. The breaks obtained at 1 : 3 and 1 : 1 molar ratios in conductometric titrations of Th^{4+} and Zr^{4+} with CAB probably indicate the formation of $RNHCl$. The disproportionation reactions of $RNHCl$ has already been reported¹ and are shown in equations (5-7).

The uv and ir spectra of the precipitates and DCB prepared by literature method⁵ were identical confirming the formation of DCB.

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References

1. H. S. YATHIRAJAN, RANGASWAMY and D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1982, 47, 1826.
2. RANGASWAMY, H. S. YATHIRAJAN and D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, *Rev. Rum. Chim.*, 1981, 26, 565.
3. RANGASWAMY, B. N. USHA and H. S. YATHIRAJAN, *Analyst*, 1984, 109, 101.

4. D. S. MAHADEVAPPA and RANGASWAMY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1976, 14, 463.
5. H. S. YATHIRAJAN, D. S. MAHADEVAPPA and RANGASWAMY, *Talanta*, 1980, 27, 52.

Intermolecular Attractive Forces at Oil/0.05% Lignosulphonate of *Eucalyptus teriticornis*-Water Interfaces

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LITERATURE reveals that surface tension and interfacial tension are the direct measure of intermolecular forces, viz. spreading coefficient, liquid/liquid phase interaction, contact angles, Girifalco-Good's constants¹ etc. The attractive forces at oil/water interfaces between unlike molecules are mainly the dispersion forces²⁻⁵. The surface free energy on the surface layer depends upon the sum of attraction forces present on the surface molecules.

The molecular attraction calculations, between dissimilar molecules are the geometric mean of the dispersion forces of the two sets of molecules. This comes directly from the original prediction of London⁶ and is confirmed for different dissimilar molecules of equal size by studying regular solutions^{7,8}. To evaluate the industrial use of any surface active agent, these parameters are the prerequisite and so the lignosulphonate of *Eucalyptus teriticornis* has been studied from this viewpoint and discussed systematically in this paper.

Experimental

Double-distilled kerosene (sp. gr., 0.7948), turpentine (sp. gr., 0.8745) and water having conductance $10^{-6} \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ were used in all the experiments.

The alcohols, viz. methanol, ethanol, n-propanol, n-butanol pentanol and sodium chloride used were of AnalaR, B.D.H. grade. The lignosulphonate from eucalyptus wood was prepared at Star Paper Mills, Saharanpur and at Cellulose and Paper Branch, Forest Research Institute, Dehradun.

Surface tension: The surface tension, having various formulations of lignosulphonate concentrations, viz., 0.01, 0.02, 0.04, 0.08 and 0.1%, lignosulphonate 0.05%+0.1% v/v alcohols, lignosulphonate 0.05%+NaCl (0.01, 0.02, 0.04, 0.08 and 0.1%), and